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Creatio Ex Nihilo And The Division By Zero

Research article

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Abstract

BACKGROUND:

The study of what is does not exclude the study of what is not. However, what exists in an objective reality in which nothing exists?

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Basic rules of classical logic and algebra were used.

RESULTS:

Under the assumption of certain conditions, indeterminate forms like $0/0$ or $1/0$ do not have to remain indeterminate.

CONCLUSION:

Zero divided by zero equals 1.

Keywords: Creatio Ex Nihilio; Nothing; Zero; Division By Zero; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

1. Introduction

As long as scientist and other authors have been trying to make some theoretical sense of a beginning of our world, various and many times each other excluding or contradicting theories have been proposed. It is very noteworthy that time and again the notion of a creation out of nothing (creatio ex negatio) often plays a central role in such theories. Today, various, very widespread monotheistic religions like Judaism, Christianity, and Islam assume and believe that God himself is the sole creator of the beginning of our world. What has the scientific notion creatio ex nihilo to do with traditional (often theistic) believe of the creation of our world out of nothing? Even so, we note a wide range of human ears aching silence among mathematicians on this topic. At one extreme, we find ultra-traditional religious beliefs and attitudes towards creatio ex nihilo in general but only very tentative attempts to approach this issue from the point of view of mathematics and science in particular. Do we have to accept once and for all that the concept creatio ex nihilo belongs beyond any doubt to the world of ideology, religion and faith and has nothing to do with science?

However, long ago the concept of nothing has been linked even to mathematics itself. Among various authros, Nicomachus of Gerasa (c. 60 – c. 120 CE), an important ancient mathematician born in Gerasa (Roman province of Syria, today Jerash, Jordan) wrote in his publication *Introduction to Arithmetic* that

“... nothing added to nothing ... makes nothing. ” (see [Nicomachus, 1926](#), pp. 237-238)

Even if a very detailed analysis of the mathematical foundations of the notion nothing is clearly beyond the scope of this publication, what can we make out of all this? In general, under conditions were zero and nothing, Latin nihilo, are taken to be identical, creatio ex nihilo, a creation out of nothing, were mathematically identical with a creation out of zero. From this point of view, the investigation of indeterminate forms like $0/0$ or $1/0$ et cetera is necessary and potentially of higher importance.

2. Material and methods

What principles could be useful and helpful and should therefore be applied in order to approach to the solution of a non solvable issue. In this context, some advice is to be found in the literature.

**“Any intelligent fool can
make things bigger, more complex, and more violent.
It takes a touch of genius —
and a lot of courage
to move in the opposite direction.”
([Schumacher, 1973](#))**

It is therefore not surprising that Albert Einstein himself arrived at a similar basic attitude. To bring it to the point, keep ‘things’ as simple and as view as possible.

**“... the supreme goal of all theory is to
make the irreducible basic elements
as simple and as few as possible ...”
([Einstein, 1934](#))**

2.1. Material

2.2. Definitions

Reaching a generally valid consensus on the definition of the numbers +0 and +1 appears to be difficult. These numbers are fundamental importance in classical logic, probability theory and so forth. The definition of the basic numbers +1 and +0 in terms of Euler's identity and physical 'constants' offer us the possibility to test classical logic or mathematical theorems et cetera by reproduce-able physical experiments too. In particular, it is very remarkable that Leibniz ([Leibniz, 1703](#)) himself published in 1703 the first self-consistent binary number system representing all numeric values while using typically +0 (zero) and +1 (one).

2.2.1. The number +0

Definition 2.1 (The number +0). Let c denote the speed of light in vacuum ([Drude, 1894](#); [Tombe, 2015](#); [Weber and Kohlrausch, 1857, 1856](#)), let ϵ_0 denote the electric constant and let μ_0 the magnetic constant. Let i denote the imaginary number ([Bombelli, 1579](#)). The number +0 is defined as the expression

$$+0 \equiv +1 - 1 \equiv + (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0) - (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0) \equiv 0 \times 1 \quad (1)$$

while '=' or \equiv denotes the equals sign ([Recorde, 1557](#)) or equality sign ([Rolle, 1690](#)) used to indicate equality and '-' ([Pacioli, 1494](#); [Widmann, 1489](#)) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus ([Recorde, 1557](#)) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

Remark 2.1. Roger Cotes (1682 – 1716) ([Cotes and Halley, 1714](#)) or Leonhard Euler's (1707 – 1783) identity ([Euler, 1748](#)) is regarded as one of the most beautiful equations ([Wilson, 2018](#)). In this context, it is provisionally presumed, that Euler's identity ([Euler, 1748](#)) is logically sound and correct while the same is not investigated in detail.

2.2.2. The number +1

Definition 2.2 (The number +1). Again, let c denote the speed of light in vacuum ([Drude, 1894](#); [Tombe, 2015](#); [Weber and Kohlrausch, 1857, 1856](#)), let ϵ_0 denote the electric constant and let μ_0 the magnetic constant. Let i denote the imaginary number ([Bombelli, 1579](#)). The number +1 is defined as the expression

$$+1 \equiv +1 + 0 \equiv +1 - 0 \equiv + (c^2 \times \epsilon_0 \times \mu_0) \quad (2)$$

while again '=' or \equiv may denote the equals sign ([Recorde, 1557](#)) or equality sign ([Rolle, 1690](#)) used to indicate equality and '-' ([Pacioli, 1494](#); [Widmann, 1489](#)) denotes minus signs used to represent the operations of subtraction and the notions of negative as well and '+' denotes the plus ([Recorde, 1557](#)) signs used to represent the operations of addition and the notions of positive as well.

2.2.3. The infinity

Definition 2.3 (The infinity). Let $+\infty$ denote positive infinity. Let $-\infty$ denote negative infinity.

Infinity may possess many properties while only a few of these properties are identified by science. However, Einstein calls us for caution in this respect.

**“Two things are infinite, the universe and human stupidity,
and I am not yet completely sure about the universe.”(Perls, 1996)**

2.2.4. Basic rules for exponentiation

Definition 2.4 (Basic rules for exponentiation). Let n denote a positive integer and let x denote any real number, then x^n corresponds to repeated multiplication as

$$x^n \equiv \underbrace{x \times x \times x \times x \dots}_{n\text{-times}} \equiv \underbrace{x^1 \times x^1 \times x^1 \times x^1 \dots}_{n\text{-times}} \equiv x^{1+1+1+1+\dots} \quad (3)$$

From this definition, some basic rules of exponentiation can be deduced. It is

$$x^a \times x^b \equiv x^{a+b} \quad (4)$$

or

$$(x \times y)^a \equiv x^a \times y^a \quad (5)$$

et cetera.

2.2.5. Planck's constant h

Planck's constant h gives the relationship between the frequency ν of a photon and its energy E . The fundamental physical constant h is of foundational importance in physics and quantum mechanics.

Definition 2.5 (Planck's constant h). Planck's constant (see [Planck, 1901](#),) h is given as

$$h = \frac{E}{\nu} \quad (6)$$

In point of fact, it is worth being noted at this point that there might exist circumstances where the energy of a photon E reduces to zero i. e. $E = 0$. What happens with Planck's constant h under these conditions? Does the same constant remain still a constant and does the same constant h have an existence in and for itself?

2.3. *Methods*

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to the something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*¹ too.

¹Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

3. Results

3.1. Zero

3.1.1. Theorem. Zero divided by zero

Theorem 1 (Zero divided by zero). *It is*

$$\frac{+0}{+0} = +0^{+0} \quad (7)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or

$$+1 = +1 \quad (8)$$

is true. Therefore, it is equally true that

$$+0 = +0 \quad (9)$$

or

$$+0^{+1} = +0^{+1} \quad (10)$$

or

$$\frac{0}{0} = \frac{0^{+1}}{0^{+1}} = 0^{+1-1} = 0^{+0} = +y \quad (11)$$

□

However, we didn't answer the question, what is 0^{+0} .

3.1.2. Theorem. Zero power zero

Theorem 2 (Zero power zero). *It is not true that*

$$+0^{+0} = +1^{+0} \quad (12)$$

Proof by modus inversus. Axiom 2 or

$$+0 = +1 \quad (13)$$

is false. Therefore, it is equally false that

$$+0^{+0} = +1^{+0} \quad (14)$$

□

3.1.3. Theorem. Zero power two

Theorem 3 (Zero power two). *It is not true that*

$$+0^{+1} = +0^{+2} \quad (15)$$

Proof by modus inversus. Axiom 2 or

$$+1 = +2 \quad (16)$$

is false. Therefore, it is equally false that

$$+0^{+1} = +0^{+2} \quad (17)$$

□

3.1.4. Theorem. Zero power n

Theorem 4 (Zero power n). *It is not true that*

$$+0^{+1} = +0^{+n} \quad (18)$$

Proof by modus inversus. Axiom 2 or

$$+1 = +n \quad (19)$$

is false (for $n \neq 1$). Therefore, it is equally false that

$$+0^{+1} = +0^{+n} = \underbrace{+0 \times +0 \times \dots}_{n \text{ times}} \quad (20)$$

□

3.1.5. Theorem. Zero power +n+1

Theorem 5 (Zero power +n+1). *It is not true that*

$$+0^{+1} = +0^{+n+1} \quad (21)$$

Proof by modus inversus. Axiom 2 or

$$+1 = +n + 1 \quad (22)$$

is false (for $n \neq 0$). Therefore, it is equally false that

$$+0^{+1} = +0^{+n+1} \quad (23)$$

□

3.1.6. Theorem. Zero power one

Theorem 6 (Zero power one). *It is not true that*

$$+0^{+1} = +1^{+1} \quad (24)$$

Proof by modus inversus. Axiom 2 or

$$+0 = +1 \quad (25)$$

is false. Therefore, it is equally false that

$$+0^{+1} = +1^{+1} \quad (26)$$

□

3.2. Unity

3.2.1. Theorem. One power zero

Theorem 7 (One power zero). *It is not true that*

$$+1^{+0} = +1^{+1} \quad (27)$$

Proof by modus inversus. Axiom 2 or

$$+0 = +1 \quad (28)$$

is false. Therefore, it is equally false that

$$+1^{+0} = +1^{+1} \quad (29)$$

□

3.2.2. Theorem. Number power zero

Theorem 8 (Number power zero). *It is not true that*

$$+2^{+0} = +3^{+0} \quad (30)$$

Proof by modus inversus. Axiom 2 or

$$+2 = +3 \quad (31)$$

is false. Therefore, it is equally false that

$$+2^{+0} = +3^{+0} \quad (32)$$

□

3.2.3. Theorem. n power zero

Theorem 9 (n power zero). *There are circumstances where*

$$+n^{+0} = (+n + 1)^{+0} \quad (33)$$

is not true.

Proof by modus inversus. Under conditions where axiom 2 or

$$+n = (+n + 1) \quad (34)$$

is false, it is equally false that

$$+n^{+0} = (+n + 1)^{+0} \quad (35)$$

□

3.2.4. Theorem. Something power zero

Theorem 10 (Something power zero). *There are circumstances where*

$$+y^{+0} = +x^{+0} \quad (36)$$

is not true.

Proof by modus inversus. Under conditions where axiom 2 or

$$+y = +x \quad (37)$$

is false, it is equally false that

$$+y^{+0} = +x^{+0} \quad (38)$$

□

3.2.5. Theorem. Something power zero

Theorem 11 (Something power zero). *There are circumstances where*

$$(+x)^{+I} = (+x)^{+I} \times (+x)^{+0} = (+x)^{+I + 0} \quad (39)$$

is true.

Proof by direct proof. Under conditions where axiom 1 or

$$+1 = +1 \quad (40)$$

is true, it is equally true that

$$(+x)^{+1} = (+x)^{+1} \quad (41)$$

According to our understanding there is something, which at this point we denote by y , whose properties are not known to us to the very detail. One property of y might be known to us. Multiplying equation 41 by y , does not change anything. It might be that

$$(+x)^{+1} = (+x)^{+1} \times y \quad (42)$$

What could be the properties of y , can y be specified in more detail? As long as we are allowed to consider the present rules of exponential calculus as valid, y can take only the value $y = +x^{+0}$. In this case, we obtain

$$(+x)^{+1} = (+x)^{+1} \times y = (+x)^{+1} \times (+x)^{+0} = (+x)^{+1+0} = (+x)^{+1} \quad (43)$$

□

Is it possible to generalize the result of the theorem 11? May we generally consider the equation

$$(x_t)^1 = (x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^0 \quad (44)$$

to be true?

3.2.6. Theorem. Equation: $(x_t)^1 = (x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^0$

Theorem 12 ($(x_t)^1 = (x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^0$). *Under appropriate conditions, the equation*

$$(x_t)^1 = (x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^0 \quad (45)$$

is true.

Proof by direct proof. Under conditions where axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true, it is equally true that

$$(x_t)^1 = (x_t)^1 \quad (46)$$

Then we suppose that the equation

$$(x_t)^1 = (x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^0 = (x_t)^1 \times \left((y_t)^0\right)^1 = \left(x_t \times (y_t)^0\right)^1 = \left(\frac{x_t \times y_t}{y_t}\right)^1 \quad (47)$$

is also true. At this point, the question arises whether we can derive a logical contradiction from this assumption? In other words, what are the immediate consequences of equation 47? Taking the logarithmus (see [Nepervs, 1614](#)) naturalis, denoted by \ln , of both sides of equation 47, no contradiction can be derived from the above equation 47. It is

$$1 \times \ln(x_t) = 1 \times \ln(x_t) + 1 \times \ln(y_t) - 1 \times \ln(y_t) = 1 \times \ln(x_t) + 0 = 1 \times \ln(x_t) \quad (48)$$

□

3.2.7. Theorem. Minus times minus

Theorem 13 (Minus times minus). *The claim*

$$-2^{+2} = +2^{+2} \quad (49)$$

is false.

Proof by mouds inversus. Axiom 2 or

$$-2 = +2 \quad (50)$$

is false. Therefore, it is equally false that

$$-2^{+2} = +2^{+2} \quad (51)$$

□

Based on theorem 13, it is not true that $-2^{+n} = +2^{+n}$. Theorem 13 may have an impact on simple binomials, trinomials and polynomials too. However, a real world experiment might illustrate this theorem in more detail. A special combination of electric or magnetic fields (an ion trap) is used to capture two negatively charged quantum mechanical entities. Mathematically, we simplify this situation as

$$-1^{+1} - 1^{+1} = -2^{+1} \quad (52)$$

Next, we add two more identical negative quantum mechanical entities as before into the same ion trap. We obtain

$$-2^{+1} - 2^{+1} = -2^{+2} = -4^{+1} \quad (53)$$

In other words, it is

$$-2^{+2} = -4^{+1} \quad (54)$$

and not $+4^{+1}$.

3.2.8. Theorem. Recursive factorial function is inconsistent.

In general, the factorial of 0, denoted as $0!$, is defined as 1, or in symbols, $0! = 1$. However, there are equally claims that the factorial of 1, denoted as $1!$, is 1, or in symbols, $1! = 1$. In the same context, the recurrence relation of the factorial function is defined as

$$n! = n(n-1)! \quad (55)$$

In the case of $n = 1$, one consequence of the recurrence relation of the factorial function is that

$$1! = 1(1-1)! = 1(0)! = 0! \quad (56)$$

Theorem 14 (Recursive factorial function is inconsistent.). *The claim, a straightforward consequence of the recurrence relation of the factorial function,*

$$1! = 0! \quad (57)$$

is false.

Proof by modus inversus. Axiom 2 or

$$+1 = +0 \quad (58)$$

is false. Therefore, it is equally false that

$$+1! = +0! \quad (59)$$

□

3.3. Division by zero

3.3.1. Theorem. Zero divided by zero I

Theorem 15 (Zero divided by zero I). *The claim*

$$\frac{+0}{+0} = \frac{+1}{+0} \quad (60)$$

is false.

Proof by modus inversus. Axiom 2 or

$$+0 = +1 \quad (61)$$

is false. Therefore, it is equally false that

$$\frac{+0}{+0} = \frac{+1}{+0} \quad (62)$$

□

3.3.2. Zero divided by zero II

Indeterminate forms like the division zero by zero appears to be a never-ending adventurous mystery that has the potential to take readers to a journey into a forbidden logical world without the possibility of return. What secrets could be hidden in such a world? To bring some light into this darkness and coldness and to approach step by step to the solution of the issue zero divided by zero let us define the following.

Definition 3.1 (The variable x_t). *Let x_t denote something completely unknown to us. However, quite independently of this the relationship*

$$(x_t)^1 \times (+0)^1 = +1^1 \quad (63)$$

is generally valid even if it is without a conceivable exception completely unimportant what x_t is or could be.

Further on we define the following relationship.

Definition 3.2 (The variable y_t). *Let y_t itself denote something completely unknown, too. The relationship*

$$(y_t)^1 \times (+1)^1 = +0^1 \quad (64)$$

might equally be generally valid. As before, it is without a conceivable exception completely unimportant what y_t could be or what y_t is.

We have to admit at this point without further ado, we do something that others don't do. Entering an unknown world in this way is a challenge in many different perspectives and it can end in a logical catastrophe. Nonetheless, what are we to do — what can we do — about that, how can two which are completely unknown to us (x_t and y_t) be able to enlighten our mind. If at all, such a question could potentially be answered especially by a controlled logically consistent proof.

Theorem 16 (The inverse relationship). *In general, the inverse relationship between the two completely unknown variables x_t and y_t is identified as*

$$(x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^1 = +1^1 \quad (65)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 is true, and therefore

$$+1^1 = +1^1 \quad (66)$$

too. Therefore, it is equally true (see equation 63) that

$$(x_t)^1 \times (+0)^1 = +1^1 \quad (67)$$

Considering equation 64 in its entirety, equation 67 itself changes somewhat. We obtain

$$(x_t)^1 \times \left((y_t)^1 \times (+1)^1 \right) = +1^1 \quad (68)$$

Simplifying equation 68 while relying on classical logic, it is generally valid that

$$(x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^1 = +1^1 \quad (69)$$

□

Even if there are many real-life examples of inverse relationships, it is completely unimportant what the content or the meaning of the two variables x_t and y_t is or could be. Equation 69 need to be obeyed and has to remain valid.

Theorem 17 (The determination of x). *The unknown value x_t is determined as*

$$(x_t)^I = \frac{+1^I}{(y_t)^I} \quad (70)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or $+1 = +1$ is true. Therefore,

$$+1^1 = +1^1 \quad (71)$$

is also true. In other words, it is equally true (see equation 69) that

$$(x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^1 = +1^1 \quad (72)$$

Dividing equation 72 by y_t , it is

$$(x_t)^1 \times \frac{(y_t)^1}{(y_t)^1} = \frac{(+1)^1}{(y_t)^1} \quad (73)$$

However, are we allowed to simplify equation 73 like

$$(x_t)^1 \times \frac{(y_t)^1}{(y_t)^1} = (x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^0 = \frac{((x_t) \times (y_t))^1}{(y_t)^1} = \left(\frac{x_t \times y_t}{y_t}\right)^1 = (x_t \times y_t^0)^1 = (x_t)^1 = \frac{+1^1}{(y_t)^1} \quad (74)$$

In conditions where $(x_t)^1 = (x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^0$ it is

$$(x_t)^1 = \frac{+1^1}{(y_t)^1} \quad (75)$$

□

Remark 3.1. *At this point, a clear message in the direction of the potentially critics is required. A critic may not accept neither the relationship $(x_t)^1 = (x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^0$ nor equation 73, nor equation 74. Equation 73 is divided by y_t while at this stage, we just don't know what is the value of y_t . For that reason, this form of argumentation is completely improper and the rest of the chain of thought collapses. Such or similar arguments are unfortunately not factually justified. We actually divide equation 73 by something unknown (y_t), which can be equal to zero. However, we are not allowed to divide by zero et cetera. Partially, this is not completely incorrect. However, operations inside equation 73 are subject to an indispensable equation, the equation 69. Whatever operation is done with equation 73, including a division by zero, equation 73 must respect equation 69 completely, it doesn't matter at all, what the value of*

$$\frac{(y_t)^I}{(y_t)^I} \quad (76)$$

or of

$$\frac{(+1)^I}{(y_t)^I} \quad (77)$$

might be at the end. It is quite clear that $\frac{(y_t)^I}{(y_t)^I}$ cannot be equal to zero. In case that $\frac{(y_t)^I}{(y_t)^I} = 0^I$, equation 73 becomes,

$$(x_t)^I \times 0^I = \frac{(+1)^I}{(y_t)^I} \quad (78)$$

which contradicts equation 63 and equation 62. In point of fact, equation 78 were true if at the same time $y_t = 1$. However, this is not the case (see equation 83). Furthermore, it is to be noted that $\frac{(y_t)^I}{(y_t)^I} = +2$ or something similar cannot be true too. In this case, we would have to accept that $(y_t)^I = 2 \times (y_t)^I$ which is a contradiction. It will remain, as we already knew, that we have to accept until further evidence to the contrary that it is something like $\frac{(y_t)^I}{(y_t)^I} = +1^0 \approx +1$.

Theorem 18 (The determination of y_t). *The unknown value y_t is determined as*

$$(y_t) = +0 \quad (79)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or

$$+1 = +1 \quad (80)$$

is true and equally

$$+0^1 = +0^1 \quad (81)$$

Therefore, it is equally true (see equation 64) that

$$(y_t)^1 \times (+1)^1 = +0^1 \quad (82)$$

At the end, the unknown variable y_t is determined as

$$(y_t)^1 = +0^1 \quad (83)$$

Theorem 19 (Zero divided by zero). *Zero divided by zero is determined as* □

$$\frac{+0^I}{+0^I} = +1^I \quad (84)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or

$$+1^1 = +1^1 \quad (85)$$

is true. Therefore, it is equally true (see equation 69) that

$$(x_t)^1 \times (y_t)^1 = +1^1 \quad (86)$$

Equation 86 changes (see equation 83), it is

$$(x_t)^1 \times (+0)^1 = +1^1 \quad (87)$$

Equation 87 changes (see equation 75), it is

$$\frac{(+1)^1}{(y_t)^1} \times (+0)^1 = +1^1 \quad (88)$$

Equation 88 changes (see equation 83). In general, the division zero by zero is determined (see Barukčić, 2017, 2018, 2019a,b, 2020a,b, 2021; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020; Barukčić and Barukčić, 2016) as

$$\frac{(+1)^1}{(+0)^1} \times (+0)^1 = \frac{(+1 \times +0)^1}{(+0)^1} = \frac{+0^1}{+0^1} = \left(\frac{+0}{+0}\right)^1 = +1^1 \quad (89)$$

□

3.3.3. Negation

Negation, Latin *negatio*, is a natural process which changes something into its own other and vice versa. Especially, in classical logic, negation is an operation which converts true or (1) to false or 0 and vice versa, false or (0) to true or (1). In the following, let $\neg(0)$ or *negation(0)* denote the logical negation of zero, let $\neg(1)$ or *negation(1)* denote the logical negation of one. However, from the point of view of philosophy and other sciences, identity, contradiction, negation and similar notions are equally mathematical descriptions of the most simple laws of objective reality. What sort of natural process is negation at the end? Mathematically, we define negation of zero as

$$\text{Negation}(0) \times 0 \equiv \neg(0) \times 0 \equiv +1 \quad (90)$$

where \neg denotes (logical (Boole, 1854) or natural) negation (Ayer, 1952; Förster and Melamed, 2012; Hedwig, 1980; Heinemann, Fritz H., 1943; Horn, 1989; Koch, 1999; Kunen, 1987; Newstadt, 2015; Royce, 1917; Speranza and Horn, 2010; Wedin, 1990). In this context, there is some evidence that

$$\text{Negation}(1) \times 1 \equiv \neg(1) \times 1 = 0 \quad (91)$$

Logically, it follows that

$$\text{Negation}(1) \equiv 0 \quad (92)$$

Under these assumptions, the following theorem follows inevitably.

Theorem 20 (Logical negation). *Algebraically, the logical operation negation \neg is given as*

$$\text{Negation}(0) = \neg(0) = \frac{+1}{+0} \quad (93)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 or

$$+1 = +1 \quad (94)$$

is true. Therefore, according to classical logic, it is equally true (see equation 90, p. 21) that

$$\text{Negation}(0) \times 0 = 1 \quad (95)$$

Considering the content of equation 91 (see p. 21) it is more or less valid something like

$$\text{Negation}(0) \times \text{Negation}(1) \times 1 = 1 \quad (96)$$

Multiplying equation 96 by (+0) it is

$$\text{Negation}(0) \times \text{Negation}(1) \times 1 \times 0 = 1 \times 0 \quad (97)$$

or

$$\text{Negation}(0) \times \text{Negation}(1) \times 0 = 0 \quad (98)$$

Equation 98 is true (see equation 17, p. 12) only if

$$\text{Negation}(0) \times \text{Negation}(1) = 1 \quad (99)$$

Equation 99 changes to

$$\text{Negation}(0) = \frac{1}{\text{Negation}(1)} \quad (100)$$

Equation 91 demands that $\text{Negation}(1) \times 1 = 0$. However, this is only true, if $\text{Negation}(1) = 0$. In this case, it is $\text{Negation}(1) \times 1 = 0 \times 1 = 0$. Based on this insight, equation 100 changes slightly. We arrive with a certain degree of evidence that the indeterminate form $1/0$ no longer remains indeterminate. It is proofed that

$$\text{Negation}(0) = \frac{1}{0} \quad (101)$$

□

Equation 101 demands equally that

$$N \times \text{Negation}(0) = \frac{N \times 1}{0} = \frac{N}{0} \quad (102)$$

3.3.4. Division of zero

The stance on the nature of mathematics is very contradictory. Paul Richard Halmos (1916 - 2006) wrote:

“Mathematics is not a deductive science—that’s a cliché. When you try to prove a theorem, you don’t just list the hypotheses, and then start to reason. What you do is trial and error, experimentation, guesswork. You want to find out what the facts are, and what you do is in that respect similar to what a laboratory technician does.”

(Halmos, 2013, p. 321)

However, it may be promising to combine the capacity of classical logic with the capacity of physics to review and improve the capabilities of mathematics. Planck’s constant h has been defined as the relationship between energy and frequency (see equation 6).

Theorem 21 (Division of zero). *Based on Planck’s constant h , it is*

$$\frac{0}{0} = 1 \quad (103)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1 (i.e. $+1 = +1$) is true. Based on this axiom, it is equally true that

$$h = h \quad (104)$$

Equation 104 can be rearranged. Therefore, it is equally true that

$$h = h \quad (105)$$

Rearranging equation 105, it is

$$h - h = h - h \quad (106)$$

and

$$\frac{h - h}{h - h} = \frac{h - h}{h - h} \quad (107)$$

We define $\left(\frac{h - h}{h - h}\right) \equiv y$. Equation 107 becomes

$$\frac{h - h}{h - h} = y \quad (108)$$

Multiplying equation 108 by $(h-h)$, it is

$$\frac{(h - h) \times (h - h)}{(h - h)} = y \times (h - h) \quad (109)$$

Simplifying equation 109, it is

$$\frac{(0^{+1}) \times (0^{+1})}{(0^{+1})} = y \times 0^{+1} \quad (110)$$

or

$$0^{+2-1} = y \times 0^{+1} \quad (111)$$

At the end, it is equally valid that

$$0^{+1} = y \times 0^{+1} \quad (112)$$

In the end, equation 112 is valid, only if $y = \frac{h-h}{h-h} = \frac{0}{0} = 1$. In this case, we obtain

$$0^{+1} = 1 \times 0^{+1} \quad (113)$$

Therefore, we must accept that

$$\frac{0}{0} = 1 \quad (114)$$

□

4. Discussion

Historically, many different authors, including Indian mathematicians too, contributed arguments for and against the division by zero. In 628 current era (CE), Brahmagupta, an Indian mathematician and astronomer claimed that $\frac{+0}{+0} = +0$. Later, around 850 CE, Mahavira, another Indian mathematician, more explicitly demanded that any number divided by zero leaves that number unchanged, so then, it is $\frac{Number}{+0} = Number$. In the following, around 1150, the Indian mathematician Bhaskara demanded that a quantity divided by zero becomes an infinite quantity or $\frac{Number}{+0} = \infty$. Later in 1656 CE, the English mathematician John Wallis, who introduced curvy symbol ∞ for infinity, advocated a similar position. In particular, the Swiss mathematician, Leonhard Euler (1707-1783), widely admired as one of the greatest mathematicians in history, discussed division by zero (see Euler, 1770, p. 48) too and supported especially the position of Bhaskara and Wallis. In the meantime, it was possible to analyze the problem of the division by zero through the different perspectives. Again and again, we were able to come to an undeniable logical conclusion. The natural process negation includes the theoretical possibility of creatio ex nihilo (Latin for ‘creation from nothing’) which refers more or less to the view that space-time itself is created out of nothing. However, this circumstance in no way justifies an ideological motivated misuse of equation 89 as scientific evidence that creatio ex nihilo is necessarily identical with a free act of God. The identification of creatio ex nihilo with a free act of God is not theoretically justified by this publication. Nonetheless, equation 89 indicates that something (+1) can be created out of nothing (+0), which could serve as a theoretical mathematical foundation of a process of creatio ex nihilo too.

5. Conclusion

In general, it is

$$\frac{+0}{+0} = +1 \quad (115)$$

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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